

ECONOMICS

STATE POLICY REGULATION ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES AND SERVICES / THE CASE OF MONGOLIA/

Tsend Chuluuntsetseg

Doctor of Economic Sciences, (Ph.D), UFE

Tudev Dorj

Academician, Doctor of Economic Sciences (Sc.D), Prof., UBEU

Geserbaatar Batmunkh

Master of Education, (MA), UFE

Tsenddorjin Dolgorsuren

Doctor of Economic Sciences (Sc.D), Prof., UBEU

Abstract

The development of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and services plays a crucial role in the socio-economic development of a country. This paper reviews the policies and regulations of the Mongolian government in this area. For instance, in implementing the goals of Mongolia's long-term development policy, "Vision 2050," the government has adopted specific SME development policies, amended the SME Support Law, and established a loan guarantee fund for SMEs. The article concludes with suggestions and recommendations for improving SME development in Mongolia.

Keywords: Vision 2050; SME Support Law; industrial park; New Revival Policy; SME Development Fund; loan guarantee; innovation; business cluster; digital solutions.

Introduction:

A key issue in economic transformation is the proper identification of factors that ensure sustainable development. The development of small and medium-sized enterprises and services plays a special role here.

Small enterprises, being flexible and mobile, play a significant role in maintaining competitive economic relations in market conditions. Since they do not hold a dominant position in the economy, they contribute to social stability as well.

The development of small and medium-sized enterprises and services is formed as a result of various forms of ownership, and by supporting competition and bringing production and services closer to consumers, they serve as a key driver for meeting demand and developing innovation.

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are defined as businesses that are small in terms of workforce and production scale, have high productivity, have flexible production technologies, and are competitive in the market.

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and services have played a major role in the economies of countries, especially developing countries, and will continue to play an important role in the socio-economic development of countries around the world. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and services account for about 90 percent of all businesses in the world, and they are considered to make an important contribution to the development of the world economy because they create a huge number of jobs.

In the successful development of Hong Kong, Taiwan and even to some extent Japan, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) play a dominant and decisive role in the economies of countries such as Japan. The dominance of very small enterprises is evident across several Asian economies. Businesses with 1–49 employees account for 92.8% of all SMEs in Hong Kong,

92.0% in Taiwan, 79.1% in South Korea, and 96.8% in Japan.

Hong Kong's SMEs are the main economic units of the country, which are relatively low-cost and highly flexible in response to changes in the business environment. SMEs account for 98% of Hong Kong's local businesses and provide two-thirds of the workforce.

The reasons for implementing SME development policies vary from country to country. For example, in the United States, SME support policies are a measure to expand the size and competitive environment.

In developing countries, SMEs help reduce unemployment. For example, in New Zealand, which has a small economy (livestock farming) with a population of about 3.5 million, similar to Mongolia, small industries and services with less than 10 employees account for almost 80 percent of all industrial establishments.

In some cases, SMEs are protected not from an industrial policy perspective, but from a social welfare perspective.

Recently, the development of SMEs has been highly valued in developing countries due to the huge business and employment opportunities they provide. Compared to developed countries, governments in developing countries consider SMEs as a strategic goal of economic development.

For example, the Japanese government is pursuing a policy of comprehensive support for SMEs for the following reasons.

1. The Japanese government has pursued a policy of comprehensive support for SMEs for reasons related to social welfare. Since the latter half of the 1950s, it has organized many SMEs as subcontractors for large parent companies in leading industrial sectors such as automobiles, electronics, and electrical machinery. In the late 1950s, the government prioritized policies aimed at increasing the competitiveness of SMEs and service providers in international markets.

The Mongolian government believes that private property is essential for developing market-based economic relations. Accordingly, it has promoted the growth of small and medium-sized businesses that are market-competitive and capable of creating jobs through production, services, and trade tailored to regional and local demand. However, the desired level of SME development has not yet been achieved.

As the number of small and medium-sized enterprises and services increases, there is a need to improve the business environment and practical support that is suitable for them.

Therefore, there is a need to study the support provided by the government for the development of small and medium-sized enterprises and services, their role and role in the socio-economic development, the business environment, pressing issues, internal regulation of operations, their management capabilities, and the comparative study of the experiences of small and medium-sized enterprises and services in other countries of the world.

In this regard, the Mongolian government's "New Revival Policy" is aimed at addressing the challenges facing medium-term economic development in the context of Mongolia's long-term development policy "Vision 2050" which aims to make Mongolia one of the leading countries in Asia in terms of social development, economic growth, and quality of life of its citizens by 2050.

In order to establish policies and guidelines for SMEs and take measures to support them, the government adopted and implemented the Law on Small and Medium Enterprises on July 27, 2007, and the Law on "Exemption of Small and Medium Enterprise Equipment from Customs and VAT" in 2009.

The Law on Supporting SMEs, adopted in 2019, provides the main legal framework for the development of SMEs, with the aim of supporting the growth of SMEs, in particular, increasing employment and increasing the contribution of SMEs to GDP.

The 2019 SME Support Law adds several new provisions regarding SMEs, and the law establishes a management and organizational system to provide various assistance and support to SMEs. These include:

- The amount of preferential loans to be provided based on annual sales and the size of the enterprise,
- Loans to micro-enterprises will be provided directly from the SME Development Fund, and loans to small and medium-sized enterprises and services will be provided through commercial banks,
- In order to participate in the services specified in the law, enterprises that meet the conditions must register as small and medium-sized enterprises and services providers;

- Various support measures will be implemented for SMEs, including training, financial support, preferential loans, equipment leasing services, tax breaks, business consulting, support for clusters, and support for entering foreign markets,

- Interest subsidies will be provided to SMEs engaged in export activities;

- SME entrepreneurs must comply with the standards, strive to improve their performance, and report on loans and other credit opportunities.

- The Mongolian State Great Khural is responsible for SME policy and financing (Article 14), while the Government approves the regional development direction for cluster development, allocates the necessary capital resources to support SMEs, and shall have broad authority to implement programs specified in the law, such as the establishment of industrial parks and free trade zones.

- Although 11 business entities have obtained special licenses to establish industrial and technological parks under the 2009 Law on the Legal Status of Industrial and Technological Parks, no such parks have actually been established in Mongolia to date. This is largely because the proposed parks have failed to meet the legal requirements.

- Although the new Law on the Legal Status of Industrial and Technological Parks adopted in 2022 has made many positive changes by expanding the regulations related to industrial and technological parks, it can be further improved in some respects based on international experience and lessons learned. Within the framework of the industrial park policy, interest in industrial parks has increased dramatically worldwide in recent decades, and many of them have developed in the areas of industry and related trade, infrastructure, and services.

In addition, organizations under the Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development, and the Small and Medium Enterprises and Services Development Fund have been established to support the activities of SMEs.

The SME Development Fund (SMEDF) was established in 2009 to address the challenges of SMEs' access to finance, but its role has been diminishing over the years. The SMEDF has provided loans to businesses for up to 5 years at an annual interest rate of 3 percent. However, businesses have been unable to apply for financing when they need it, despite the fact that the fund's announcements have failed to meet their needs, and the SMEDF has failed to adapt its operations to meet the needs of SMEs. Despite an increase in the number of loan applicants between 2018 and 2020, the SMEDF's total budget and the number of projects financed have decreased significantly. The fund was able to finance only 14-16 percent of the project applications it received, so it financed only a small percentage of the needs.

Table 4.9.

Number of companies that received financing from the SME Development Fund in 2009-2022

Loan period	Total number of borrowers	Total loan amount disbursed
2009	1638	38,629,354.00
2010	1607	40,012,796.00
2011	1768	315,113,397.00
2012	104	25,579,700.00
2013	538	71,999,832.92
2014	928	143,838,900.00
2015	398	60,269,112.00
2016	188	79,980,720.50
2017	154	49,789,910.00
2018	212	96,372,930.00
2019	451	47,444,316.25
2020	249	22816441.00
2021	12	810,000.00
2022	156	19,181,814.00
2023	8403	1,011,848,223.67
2025	8696	1,000,801.446.70

Source: Information from the SME Policy and Planning Department of the Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Rural Development, 2025

However, some problems related to the macroeconomic situation, social, legal implementation, infrastructure and financing still pose difficulties for SMEs in our country.

Article 15,1,4 of Chapter 5 of the Law on Small and Medium Enterprises provides for financial support for SMEs and improvement of their equity adequacy.

In 2020, the SME Development Fund (SMEDF) was transformed into an SME Agency with limited responsibilities in the field of financial access. After the SMEDF was accused of lack of transparency in the process of granting loans, the SME Agency was established by merging the SMEDF and the SME Agency of the Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Rural Development. While the direct role of the SME Agency in providing financing has been limited to providing loans to micro-enterprises due to the reduction in budget allocation, the Government is working to support the Credit Guarantee Fund as a tool to help SMEs obtain long-term financing sources from commercial banks.

In order to ensure transparency and fairness in the operation of SME land loans, an electronic application system has been introduced. The system operates in four main stages: first, a loan officer reviews the application; second, a team of experts makes a selection; third, an on-site visit to the project; and fourth, an assessment of the project's potential and makes a decision.

Established under the name "SME Development Fund", it provides financing to individual entrepreneurs and small and medium-sized enterprises in other sectors, in addition to the agricultural sector specified in the SME Law.

One thing that is observed in developed countries is that a bank can develop and implement an independent system within the bank when it has hundreds of thousands of corporate borrowers, but in reality, only one bank uses a system that calculates interest rates based on risk. In order to reduce lending rates, there are

many factors, including supporting measures to increase deposit rates, developing the capital market, creating an interbank market, diversifying the purchase market, and more diligent operations of commercial banks, as well as the effectiveness of risk management. Japan's experience offers a useful model for Mongolia. In Japan, the guarantee rate of the Credit Guarantee Association is based on estimated default probabilities and published by the Credit Risk Database (CRD). This approach could serve as a reliable reference for Mongolia when determining its own credit guarantee rates.

When introducing the Credit Risk Database (CRD), it is necessary to clarify how to deal with the initial data, such as credit information of commercial bank borrowers, information on enterprises, and information on late and non-payment of loan repayments.

As mentioned earlier, Mongolia needs to clarify its legal framework, including the "Law on Corporate Secrecy" and the "Law on the Protection of Personal Secrets," and it is also important to consider the legal regulations applicable to institutional financing, such as the Collateral System and the SME Fund.

One of the priorities of the SME Department is to strengthen its budget and technical capacity and to reach out to the regional level. The SME Department lacks the capacity to reach rural areas, where the majority of SMEs are located.

The Law on SME Support pays special attention to supporting cluster development, and in order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to develop a methodology for developing SME cluster development. The law defines a cluster as "an enterprise that cooperates in a coordinated manner in terms of production and service objectives, types, directions, and geographical locations in the form of cooperation and diversification," and states that clusters will be supported by providing comprehensive tax and financial support, improving infrastructure provision, and creating conditions for cooperation, diversification, and collaboration in their activities. Most importantly, industry associations support the establishment of SME-based clusters. Cluster-

based approaches may be useful or appropriate for light industries (including wool and leather industries) as a mechanism to reduce costs by creating shared facilities. For example, in the leather sector, this could include raw material storage, centralized wastewater treatment facilities, and efficient supply chain logistics. The SME Department is responsible for cluster development, but the methodology and overall capacity required to implement the provisions on cluster development contained in the SME Law are limited.

Therefore, the SME Department should focus on addressing the challenges faced by SMEs in accessing financial and high-quality professional advisory services by coordinating its activities with ministries and cities involved in cluster development and by improving coordination of work.

The SME Department should play a key role in enabling SMEs to access digital or e-solutions tailored to their company and business needs. Digital solutions can reduce transaction costs in several ways. They improve access to information and enhance communication among employees, suppliers, and business networks. They also lower transportation and border operation costs. Furthermore, by expanding service scopes and integrating data analytics, digital tools increase access to domestic and global markets, finance, training, employment, and public services while supporting innovation.

The Issue of digitalization of the "economy" has been a priority goal of Mongolia's state policy in recent years, as reflected in the "Vision 2050" Mongolia's long-term development policy and the goals of the New Renaissance Policy adopted in 2020. Important steps have been taken so far, including the adoption and implementation of 10 laws, including the Law on Electronic Signatures, the Law on Personal Data Protection, and the Law on Virtual Asset Service Providers, which came into effect in May 2022.

Although the Mongolian government has taken policy and regulatory measures to develop small and medium-sized enterprises and services and is focusing on improving the legal environment, the role that small and medium-sized enterprises and services play in the economic and social development of our country is not very effective.

The most difficult issue for SMEs is financing. These include high interest rates, strict terms, lack of collateral, lack of access to preferential loans from international organizations and governments, and lack of sales of manufactured products.

Although the Mongolian government has provided a significant amount of preferential loans and interest rate subsidies to support the development of SMEs in recent years, the coverage is still limited due to a lack of credit sources.

References

1. Barbard, C. (2010). *The Functions of the Executive*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
2. Blinov, A. N. (2025). *Small and Medium Enterprises and Big Politics*.
3. Dolgorsuren, Ts. (2008). *Some Issues in the Management of Small and Medium Enterprises in Mongolia*. Ulaanbaatar.
4. Dorj, T., & Chimed, U. (2000). *Management* (pp. 10–13, 78–81). Ulaanbaatar.
5. *Economic Survey*. (n.d.). Retrieved from <http://www.economicsurvey.com>
6. *Gosudarstvo and Financial Business*. (2019). Moscow: INION RAN.
7. Grachyov, I. D., & Belova, I. V. (2018).
8. Jeol Corman, & Lusser, R. N. (2023). *Small Business Management: A Planning Approach* (p. 307). Irwin.
9. Kiyazev, V. G. (2024). *Taxes as a Mechanism for Stimulating Small Entrepreneurship*. Financial, (1).
10. *Korean Small Business Corporation*. (2024). *Training Program for SME Managers: Development Process of the Korean Economy and SMEs*.
11. Llapusta, M. G., & Starostin, Y. L. (2019). *Small and Medium Entrepreneurship*. Moscow: INFRA-M.
12. Megginson, L., Burd, M. J., Scott, C. R., & Megginson, L. C. (2023). *Small Business Management: Legal Forms of Ownership*. Irwin McGraw-Hill.
13. *Mongolia's Vision 2050 and New Recovery Policy (NRP)*. (2025).
14. Novikov, V., & Sheregi, F. (2025). *Small Business Enterprise and Banks: Diverging Paths*. *Russian Economic Journal*, (4).
15. *Outline of Small and Medium Enterprise Policies of the Japanese Government*. (2019). Small and Medium Enterprise Agency, MITI.
16. *Resource Center for Support of Small and Medium Enterprises*. (2019). Moscow, (3).
17. Samarukha, V. I., Sachkov, D. I., Gulyaeva, L. V., Gushchina, I. V., Khitrova, E. M., & Starodubtseva, E. A. (2024). *Basic Entrepreneurial Activity*. Irkutsk: BGUEP Publishing House.
18. Shamalov, F. (2025). *Small Entrepreneurship*. *Economist*, (2).
19. *State Great Khural of Mongolia*. (2019). *Law on Support of Small and Medium Enterprises and Services*. Retrieved from <https://legalinfo.mn/mn/detail/14525>
20. United Nations. (2020). *Economic Diversification in Some Landlocked Developing Countries in Asia*.
21. Vilenskiy, A. (2024). *Stages of Development of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in Russia*. *Economic Questions*, (8).
22. Vorzimer, L. H. (n.d.). *U.S. Small Business Administration: Using Census Data to Select Store Sites*. *Small Marketers AID* No. 16.
23. World Bank. (2024). *Industrial Park Circular Economy: Technologies of Competitiveness*.
24. World Bank. (2025). *Global Economic Outlook and Developing Countries*.
25. *World Bank Mongolia*. (n.d.). Retrieved from <http://www.worldbank.org/mn>
26. *World Factbook*. (n.d.). Retrieved from <http://www.worldfactbook.com>
27. *World Trade Organization*. (n.d.). Retrieved from <http://www.wto.org>